

A Single-Line Case Study on Avabahuka

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Abstract

. *Avabahuka* can be correlated with a Frozen shoulder. In this condition, *Vata* is localized in the shoulder region, getting aggravated due to injury to *Agni Karma* dries up *Shleshaka Kapha* and the bindings (ligaments) of the shoulders, constricts the *Snayu* and *Siras* present there, and produces *Avabahuka* were as *Agni karma* is a method of pain relive Acharya Sushruta, a renowned Vedic Indian surgeon has very well explained the eminence of *Agnikarma* by saying that the recurrence of disease will not be there if once they are treated with *Agnikarma*. He in his text mentioned various *Dravyas* according to the diseases through which *Agnikarma* can be performed. Also, several *Dahanaupkarana* are mentioned in the classics that provide practitioners abundant methods to perform *Agnikarma* without much limitations hence, the present study is planned to compare the evaluation of *Agni karma* by hand *Avabahuka*.

Material methods- The clinical study patient was treated by a shaman and *Agni karma* for 7 days.

Keywords - *Agni Karma* , *Avabahuka* , *Shleshaka Kapha*, frozen shoulder

INTRODUCTION

Due to sedentary work, increasing competition, heavy weight lifting, swimming, cricket, and vigorous use of advanced computer applications, all cause the deformity of ligaments and muscles of the shoulder joint. This leads to disability of the *Amsa Sandhi* and *Bahu* which results in *Avabahuka* (Frozen shoulder) that obstructs the day-to-day activities of human beings. Among the *Dosha*, *Vata Dosha* is superior in all aspects, most powerful in its ability & activity. *Vata* is a motivating factor for *Pitta* & *Kapha*, which is vitiated by such a lifestyle. In today's fast & mechanical life, *Vataja* disorders occupy the top position in the field of pathological conditions.

Frozen shoulder, "Peri-arthritis" or "Adhesive Capsulitis" is a disease of the shoulder region in which the shoulder capsule, the connective tissue surrounding the glenohumeral joint of the shoulder, becomes inflamed and stiff, greatly restricting motion and causing chronic pain. It causes a significant loss of both, Active Range of Motion (AROM) and Passive Range of ROM.

NEED OF STUDY

As mentioned in our Ayurveda classics Agni having Ushna Guna (hot property) leads to the pacification of Vata-Kapha Doshas and further increases Dhatwagni. In doing so, it breaks the pathology of the disease along with a reduction in pain. Agnikarma plays a significant role in relieving pain in diseases with musculoskeletal.

Frozen shoulders are a common source of concern. Even though the disease is not fatal, its symptoms make the patient uncomfortable and hamper their day-to-day activities. Modern medicine's management is conservative, such as rest, immobilization, and the use of analgesics, anti-inflammatory drugs, or surgical intervention in the later course of the disease. All of these have their drawbacks in the form of complications such as liver diseases, kidney diseases, wound infections, prolonged rest, and so on, as well as being a costly affair. Because conservative treatment with drugs must be continued regularly for an extended period, there is a need for research in *Agni* karma management which is efficacious and cost-effective with minimum side effects in a small setup.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

- To study the effect of stimulation of *Marma* points by hand in the management of *Avabahuka Roga* (frozen shoulder).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A 35-year-old Male patient, a Farmer by profession presented with complaints of pain, stiffness, and limited movements of the right shoulder joint for 10 months. He had met with trauma by falling from a bike 6 and a half months before. Initially, he had pain only at night and later on too.

History

The no K/C/O-

Personal history

- Appetite-Good
- Diet-Mixed type
- Sleep-Reduced for 6 months
- Micturition-Normal
- Bowel-Normal
- Addiction-Not found
- Family history:

- Maternal-not specific
- Paternal-not specific
- Self- Married; 1 son 1 daughter

General examination

- G.C.-Good
- Pulse-80/min
- B.P.-110/70 mm of hg
- Icterus-Not found
- Pallor-Not found
- Lymphadenopathy-Not found Systemic examination
- RS: AE=BE, Clear
- CVS: S1S2 normal, no abnormal sound added
- CNS- CNS- Conscious & Oriented
- P/A- Soft and non-tender

Local examination

- Muscle tone: Normal
- Deformity of right shoulder joint- Absent
- Tenderness- tenderness present
- Local temperature- Normal
- Restriction of movements with severe pain
- Restriction range of Movements:
 - Abduction- 60°
 - Flexion- 45°
 - Extension- 50°
 - Internal rotation: Severe pain with the Dorsum of a hand touching L2 only

Diagnosis Left frozen shoulder. Management marma karma was done as per the following.

Agni karma Therapy

Pre-operative Measures

Proper assessments were made before going for the Agnikarma. Patient counseling was done. The instruments required during the process were kept ready.

The treatment was followed for 7 sittings daily for one week.

Operative Measures

Proper examination and cleaning was done. The site was marked with a pen or marker and then Agnikarma was performed by Panchadhatu shalakaha. Agnikarma was done until the Samyak Dagdha Lakshana appears

Postoperative

After the procedure, Madhu and Ghrita were applied to the Samyak Dagdha wound. Agnidagdha Vrana was applied to the patient, and a proper diet was maintained.

Table 1: Avabahuka (frozen shoulder).

Sr	Criteria	Before Treatment	After treatment
1	Pain	Severe	Mild
2	Stiffness	Severe	Mild
3	Range of Rotation	45 degrees	170 degrees
4	Internal rotation	Severe pain with Dorsum of hand touching to L2 only	Mild pain with the dorsum of a hand touching to scapular region

DISCUSSION

The diseases in which Agnikarma is indicated are due to vitiation of Vata and Kapha so it is considered better therapy to pacify these Doshas. Also due to Ushana, Sukshama, Teekshana, and Ashukari Guna of Agni, it pacifies Vata-Kapha Doshas. Ayurveda believes in the concept of Dhatwagni where each and every Dhatu possess its own Dhatwagni.

When this Agni becomes low, diseases begin to manifest and in this condition, Agnikarma works efficiently. When external heat is applied at the site through red hot Shalaka the Dhatwagni increases which helps in digestion of the aggravated Doshas thus curing the disease.

Application of Agni or local heat increases the local temperature which enhances the perfusion and does efficient delivery of oxygen to the tissues. Because of the better blood perfusion ischemia and degeneration-related tissue injury get healed. There is clearance of local inflammatory mediators so inflammation is resolved and finally, pain is reduced. Agnikarma also stimulates DPI (descending pain

CONCLUSION- A single case study shows the effectiveness of Agni in the management of a Frozen shoulder without any internal medication or major surgical procedure. It is a simple and safe OPD-level procedure with cost-effectiveness. Especially it is instant pain relief. It causes no injury or minimal injury and hence gives the least adverse effects. This technique is somewhat neglected by many Ayurvedic practitioners. It is required to explore this procedure in different kinds of pain management.

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